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Research Paper

The Soda Industry and Energy Efficiency

Sugar, Diabetes, and Health Care Costs

The Soda Industry seems like a strange topic for an energy efficiency discussion. On the surface, how much energy could bottled sugar water really use? A good starting point is to look at the strong link between sugar and diabetes. In a study by Basu, Yoffe, Hills and Lustig, they state that nearly 1 in 10 adults worldwide is affected by diabetes, with most of the rise being linked to type 2 Diabetes, or “adult onset” diabetes.¹ Further, they go on to show that sugar availability has a strong linear correlation with diabetes prevalence as shown in the scatterplot.

Working under the assumption that sugar is strong suspect in diabetes, it is helpful to see the impact this has on the healthcare industry and later energy efficiency. The CDC estimates that, **at least**, 1 in 10 healthcare dollars is attributed to diabetes.² A statistical brief published by the Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project noted that nearly one in five hospitalizations were related to patients with diabetes.³ The brief goes on to say in addition, hospital stays for patients with diabetes were longer, more costly and more likely to originate in the emergency department.

Sugars Relationship to Total Energy Consumed By Healthcare

It is a reasonable further assumption to equate dollars spent with energy used in the health care industry. Although, in the case of diabetes, there appears to be strong evidence that it may be even more energy intensive, due to the reliance on equipment such as dialysis machines, which are often used for the rest of the life of the patient. In looking at energy use by Healthcare, it is estimated to be about 4% of the total energy consumed in the United States, according the Department of Energy.⁴ One other way of looking at this energy cost is to note that Nuclear Electric Power accounts for 8% of all of our energy produced in the United States.⁵ The amount of ***energy consumed by Health Care then is equivalent to half of all of the energy produced by Nuclear Power in the United States (as shown below).***

Figure 2.0 Primary Energy Consumption by Source and Sector, 2011
(Quadrillion Btu)

Out of that pool of energy on health care, a rough heuristic would be to say that between 10% to 20% of energy consumed, **at least**, is due to diabetes, which in turn is most likely type 2 diabetes, which is most likely influenced by sugar intake according the research presented earlier.

Solution To Rising Energy Use In Health Care: Tackle the Soda Problem

Working under these assumptions: Sugar is a major cause in Diabetes, and Diabetes Care is a significant consumer of energy in the Healthcare industry, it would then be logically to figure out where all of this sugar is coming from. A first logical stopping point to limiting sugar intake would be to look at what food contains the highest amount of sugar, and also which food, that is high is sugar is consumed in the greatest quantities.

Sugar water producers, i.e., soda companies are in fact, guilty on both counts.

An infographic produced by Slate and Euronomintor International shows that a typical US citizen purchased 170 liters of this sugar water per year, which equates to about a half a liter of sugar water a day (as shown below).

Experts in the Energy Efficiency industry would be wise to take on the sleeping soda giant. The health effects of soda are just one factor in energy efficiency equation. The energy consumed in the production and transportation of sugar water is also significant. Soda manufactures may turn out to be our generation's tobacco companies, but unlike the tobacco problem, we appear to be asleep at the wheel.

References

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